

Research Article

Distribution of Nigerian Youth Population and National Development

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Abstract

This study is aimed at examining the population composition of Nigerian youth in terms of distribution and structure (age and sex). Secondary data was obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics in collaboration with Federal Ministry of Youth Development (National Baseline Youth Survey 2012) for the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria were used. A population pyramid representing the sex (male and female) and the age interval (15-19, 20-24, 25-29 and 30-35) years were constructed for the zones to show the distribution of youth estimated based on the age range, we obtained the percentage(probability) of the various age group. Chi-Square analysis was also used to look at the relationship between states and age structure of youths in Nigeria. Finally the study checks for the state with the highest and lowest probability of youth in each geopolitical zone. Conditional probabilities were also estimated for the six geopolitical zones. The study reveals that the female genders are higher than the male gender and that age distribution is not associated with states. The study recommends that government should come up with policies and programme directed towards youth re-orientation for an all-inclusive national development.

Keywords: Age, Composition, Gender, Probability and Youth

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Introduction

Nigeria known as the “Giant of Africa” is the most populous country in Africa with a population of 140 million people, based on the 2006 National Population Census and 163 million based on National Population Commission’s estimates. Nigeria accounts for about approximately one – sixth of the Africa’s population. 50% of Nigerians are urban

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dwellers. Variety of customs, languages and traditions among Nigeria's 389 ethnic groups gives the country's cultural diversity. Nigeria population is largely dominated by three ethnic groups – Yoruba, Hausa-Fulani and Igbo. The Yoruba are in the West, the Hausa-Fulani in the North and Igbo in the East. However, there are hundreds of other ethnic groups of a wide ranging population sizes. Among these are Urhobo, Itsekiri, Bini, Ishan, Isoko, Ijaw, Ukwuani, Idoma, Igala, Igbira, Kanuri, Ibibio, Efic, Ogoni, Oron, etc. (NBS, 2010).

The change in any population is caused by three main important factors; Birth rate, Death rate and higher rate Migration. If the change is caused by the birth rate, there will be higher percentage of young people and children in the population. If the change is caused by death rate, there will be higher percentage of the old people in the population. Furthermore, if the change is caused by high net migration rate, there will be large number of people between the ages of 16 – 50 years. Nigeria surge in population is caused by birth rate, crude Birth rate of Nigeria in 2003 by the National Demography and Health Survey (NDHS) was 4.20, and this implied that there is high crude Birth Rate in Nigeria.

The youths are a very important part of the increasing population of Nigeria. They are very effective in both nation building and the general development of the country as larger proportion of the population are youth aged between 15-53 years (NBS, 2012). It is therefore, important for us to determine the population distribution of the youth around the country for positive maximum national benefit. Against this background there is need to undertake a study to obtain the distribution, structure and if necessary composition and change in population to enable stakeholders planned appropriately.

Review of Literature

Adekoya and Ajilore (2012) revealed that the communication policy in the country if properly implemented is indeed suitable for empowering the growth and development of the Nigerian state. Odoh, Okechukwu and Innocent (2012) in a paper 'Role of the Youths in National Development' found that policies to address the challenges facing youths have not resulted in a great deal of success. He further attribute the failures to a number of factors which included the inadequacy of information about youths that is necessary in the design of policy, weak coordination amongst government agencies, donors, regional organizations, and the failure to design specific policies that are suited to deal with the problems of African youths.

Ifenkwe (2012) suggested that the youth should be given recognition by the community leadership and relevant organs of government in order to give the group legal status. In addition to assist in identifying community needs and anxieties as well as in addressing such issues they should be alive to their social responsibilities as youths. For instance Surveillance and vigilante services clean-up activities and representing the community in football and other competitions. Therein lays the key to sustainable community and rural development in Nigeria.

Sunday and Mariam (2015) Opined that Nigerian government must revitalize its economy, reduce unemployment progressively, and generate more employment opportunities for sustainable development, a paradigm shift in policy that is critical to effective entrepreneurship development becomes imperative.

Methodology

The study uses secondary data obtained from NBS (National Baseline Youth survey, 2012), for the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. A population pyramid representing the sex (male and female) and the age interval (15-19, 20-24, 25-29 and 30-35) years were constructed for the zones. This was intended to show the distribution of youth estimated based on the age range, and determined the percentage (probability) of the various age groups. Chi-Square analysis was also used also to look at the relationship between states and age structure of youths in Nigeria.

Results and Discussions

Having collected the required and organized the data for the research. Below are the results and discussions that follow.

Figure a and b below show the south – East zone population pyramids by state and the age interval

Fig (a) Population pyramid by state

Fig (b) Population Pyramid by Age

Figures c and d would show the south – south zone population pyramid by state and the age interval

Fig. (d) Population Pyramid by State

Fig. (d) Population Pyramid by Age

The figures c and d will show the South – West Zone population pyramid by state and age interval.

Figures a and b are the population pyramid of the north – central by state and the age intervals.

Fig. “a:” and “b” below shows the North – East zone population pyramid by state and the age interval.

Fig 3.1.6a and 3.1.6b below shows the North – West zone population pyramid by state and the age interval.

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Table1 Probability of South - East

STATE	SEX	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 35
ABIA	Male	0.15	0.09	0.08	0.014
	Female	0.16	0.13	0.07	0.17
ANAMBRA	Male	0.19	0.09	0.09	0.11
	Female	0.16	0.10	0.13	0.13
EBONYO	Male	0.19	0.12	0.10	0.09
	Female	0.19	0.08	0.14	0.08
ENUGU	Male	0.15	0.16	0.14	0.19
	Female	0.15	0.16	0.14	0.12
IMO	Male	0.18	0.14	0.09	0.10

Table 2: Probability of South-south

STATE	SEX	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 35
AKWA- IBOM	Male	0.11	0.10	0.14	0.16
	Female	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.16
BAYELSA	Male	0.10	0.12	0.11	0.11
	Female	0.8	0.14	0.18	0.18
CROSS-RIVER	Male	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.08
	Female	0.15	0.13	0.17	0.12
DELTA	Male	0.12	0.17	0.09	0.08
	Female	0.18	0.13	0.12	0.11
EDO	Male	0.16	0.12	0.11	0.12
	Female	0.12	0.13	0.11	0.012
RIVERS	Male	0.16	0.13	0.09	0.13
	Female	0.12	0.10	0.16	0.11

Table 3: Probability of North-East

STATE	SEX	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 35
ADAMAWA	Male	0.17	0.14	0.09	0.10
	Female	0.16	0.10	0.10	0.14
BAUCHI	Male	0.18	0.08	0.09	0.14
	Female	0.16	0.12	0.12	0.11
BORNO	Male	0.20	0.07	0.05	0.16
	Female	0.14	0.12	0.08	0.17
GOMBE	Male	0.13	0.07	0.07	0.17
	Female	0.17	0.13	0.11	0.14
TARABA	Male	0.16	0.13	0.11	0.13
	Female	0.10	0.13	0.14	0.10
YOBE	Male	0.19	0.12	0.09	0.10
	Female	0.15	0.11	0.11	0.13

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Table 4 probability of North-West

STATE	SEX	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 35
JIGAWA	Male	0.15	0.12	0.09	0.13
	Female	0.14	0.13	0.10	0.15
KADUNA	Male	0.14	0.09	0.10	0.13
	Female	0.16	0.13	0.12	0.14
KANO	Male	0.16	0.08	0.07	0.12
	Female	0.13	0.11	0.15	0.17
KATSINA	Male	0.19	0.11	0.10	0.10
	Female	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.15
KEBBI	Male	0.16	0.10	0.09	0.15
	Female	0.11	0.14	0.12	0.13
SOKOTO	Male	0.18	0.09	0.12	0.11
	Female	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.15
ZAMFARA	Male	0.14	0.06	0.04	0.09
	Female	0.16	0.10	0.13	

Table 5: Probability of South-West

STATE	SEX	15 - 19	20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 35
EKITI	Male	0.19	0.12	0.07	0.09
	Female	0.20	0.14	0.08	0.11
LAGOS	Male	0.12	0.10	0.13	0.16
	Female	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.16
OGUN	Male	0.12	0.08	0.10	0.12
	Female	0.16	0.11	0.11	0.19
ONDO	Male	0.17	0.16	0.12	0.09
	Female	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.12
OSUN	Male	0.15	0.08	0.09	0.13
	Female	0.17	0.11	0.09	0.13
OYO	Male	0.14	0.11	0.10	0.13
	Female	0.17	0.10	0.10	0.14

Table 6: Probability of North-Central

STATE	SEX	15 – 19	20 – 24	25 – 29	30 – 35
BENUE	Male	0.22	0.12	0.10	0.13
	Female	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.08
KOGI	Male	0.16	0.12	0.12	0.10
	Female	0.13	0.15	0.11	0.11
KWARA	Male	0.18	0.10	0.08	0.09
	Female	0.24	0.10	0.11	0.10
NASARAWA	Male	0.17	0.12	0.10	0.12
	Female	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.18
NIGER	Male	0.16	0.06	0.06	0.14
	Female	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.6
PLATEAU	Male	0.13	0.09	0.06	0.15
	Female	0.14	0.13	0.16	0.13
FCT (Abuja)	Male	0.10	0.12	0.15	0.16
	Female	0.10	0.12	0.13	0.12

Table 7: Population of youth in Nigeria in the six geopolitical Zones by sex

	SE	SS	SW	NC	NE	NW
Male	352368	5307687	60911633	4726789	4302258	7057678
Female	3858943	5503741	6427167	4851194	4389782	8046681
National	7382211	10811426	12518800	9577963	8692040	15104339

Table 8: Probability of Male and Female in the Six Geopolitical Zones in Nigeria by sex

	SE	SS	SW	NC	NE	NW
Male	0.480	0.490	0.490	0.490	0.490	0.4880
Female	0.520	0.510	0.510	0.510	0.510	0.520
National	0.115	0.167	0.195	0.149	0.136	0.232

Fig. 3.2: A three diagram showing the probabilities the six geopolitical zones and sex (Males/Females)

Summary of Major Findings

This study through population pyramid gives an illustration of the distribution of youth in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Anambra having the highest population in the South - East, River for the South - South, Lagos for the South - West, Benue for North Central, Bauchi for the North - East and Kano for the North - West zone.

The population distribution of each states in the six geopolitical zones helps us know the percentage of male and female of each age interval for each state in the zones for instance, the probability that the male in Abia state of the range of 15 - 19 years is 0.15 and that of female of the same range is 0.16 and this goes on for all other age interval. We knowing that the probability of any outcome or event is always between 0 and 1 so therefore, the summation of the probabilities of male and female of the ages from 15 - 25 years is 1.

In the South - East, the conditional probability that youth from ages 15 - 35 years are males is 0.114 that of the female is 0.151. In the south - south has the conditional probability for the same age group of male is 0.039 while for female is 0.166. The conditional probability for male in the age range of 15 - 35 years who are said to be from the South - West is 0.197 while that of the female is 0.194. The conditional probability of male in the age interval 15 - 35 years who are said to be from the North Central is 0.156 and that of the female is 0.144. In the North - East, the conditional probability of male is 0.137 and for the female is 0.135. The conditional probability of youth in the age interval 15- 35 years who are from the North - West and male is 0.233 and that of the female is 0.239.

Using the analysis of Chi-Square to check the association between the age group distribution and states, it was observed that the percentage of the age interval 30-35 years is larger than the age interval 15-19 years. States like Benue, Kwara, Nasarawa, Ondo and Oyo have lower percentage of age interval 15-19 years showing that there population was affected negatively (reduced) in the near future.

After the summation of the population of each age interval of every with respect to state in the six geopolitical zones it was found that the female gender is rating higher than the male gender. In the probability distribution South - East and North - West has the same probability of 0.48 i.e 48%, while south - South, South -west, North Central and North - East has same probability of 0.49 for the male gender. For the female gender, south - South, North Central, South - West and North _East has 0.57 probabilities.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This research work has been able to construct population pyramid, probability distribution and conditional probabilities for the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria by age interval and sex. We were able to identify in each zone, the state with the highest population and the highest probability of males and females in each of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria and that

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